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Dr. R. Mayakkannan

HEALTH CARE MANAGEMENT IN INDIA: SOME ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

Dr. A. Akhanna¹ & Dr. R.S. Gupta² (R. 40, A. 2011)

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, KJ Somaiya Institute of Health Sciences, Mumbai, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, KJ Somaiya Institute of Health Sciences, Mumbai, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, KJ Somaiya Institute of Health Sciences, Mumbai, India

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, KJ Somaiya Institute of Health Sciences, Mumbai, India

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, KJ Somaiya Institute of Health Sciences, Mumbai, India

ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is to study the developments in Indian health care sector and will touch upon the rising demand of health care sector in India. The study will evolve the concept of globalization, development of information technology, medical tourism, role of urbanization, growth of health care insurance sector, affordability of health care in India and the role played by major private health care firms in India.

Study design

Descriptive design.

Methods

Data used here is secondary data, and collection of data is done from different health care surveys in India, health care websites, journals, newspapers, health magazines and conferences.

Results

Rising demand of health care in India, India is one among the leading developing countries in health care as the demand of this sector is expected to reach US\$ 100 billion by 2015 from the current US\$ 65 billion, growing at around 20 per cent a year, according to rating agency Fitch, and the major factors driving the growth in the sector include increasing population, growing lifestyle related health issues, cheaper costs for treatment, thrust in medical tourism, improving health insurance penetration, increasing disposable income, government initiatives and focus on Public-Private Partnership (PPP) models.

Conclusion

With rising health care demand in India, private sector hospitals and health care firms started to come with the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) by giving subsidized rates and rural coverage concepts in India, so that the poor people can afford the necessary treatment, as 32.7 per cent of the total Indian people fall below the international poverty line of US\$ 1.25 per day (PPP) while 68.7 per cent live on less than US\$ 2 per day (www.wikipedia.org).

United Poverty and Human Development Initiative (UPHI) stated in 2010, that eight Indian states have more poor people than 20 poorest African nations combined which tends to more than 410 million poor in the poorest African countries.

Keywords: Health, challenges, technology, globalization, urbanization

INTRODUCTION

'Health is Wealth', this word is being used as a common slogan concept from ages, but the present scenario of life has made it an alarming concept in human minds even though it was a old one, but is a newly one in today's changing environmental scenario. It is also fully processed since the different terminology within different countries.

Hospitals aimed at smaller towns and cities, with a target of 25 hospitals in three years. The company is also launching a nationwide Mother and Child Programme for the poor under the aegis of the Fortis Foundation (The Hindu 2012).

HEALTH CARE ISSUES IN INDIA

Malnutrition

Malnutrition is the condition that results from taking an unbalanced diet in which certain nutrients are lacking, in excess (too high an intake), or in the wrong proportions (Brieff 2009). Forty-two per cent of India's children below the age of three are malnourished, which is greater than the statistics of sub-Saharan African region of 28 per cent. Although India's economy grew 50 per cent from 2001–06, its child-malnutrition rate only dropped 1 per cent, lagging behind countries of similar growth rate. Malnutrition impedes the social and cognitive development of a child, reducing his educational attainment and income as an adult (Robinson 2008). These irreversible damages result in lower productivity.

Diseases

A disease is an abnormal condition affecting the body of an organism. It is often contrasted to be a medical condition associated with specific symptoms and signs (Disease, Oxford's Medical Dictionary). It may be caused by factors originally from an external source, such as infectious disease, or it may be caused by internal dysfunctions, such as auto immune diseases. In humans, 'disease' is often used more broadly to refer to any condition that causes pain, dysfunction, distress, social problems, or death to the person afflicted or similar problems for those in contact with the person. Diseases such as dengue fever, hepatitis, tuberculosis, malaria and pneumonia continue to plague India due to increased resistance to drugs (Dengue, Centres for Disease Control and Prevention US 2011). And in 2011, India developed a totally drug-resistant form of tuberculosis (Gold vent 2012). India is ranked 3rd among the countries with the most HIV-infected (HIV/AIDS, UNICEF India 2011). Diarrhoeal diseases are the primary causes of early childhood mortality (Life Expectancy and Mortality in India, The Prajnapaya Foundation 2011). These diseases can be attributed to poor sanitation and in safe-quality safe drinking water in India (Health Conditions, US Library of Congress 2011). However, in 2012 India was polio free for the first time in its history (India marks one year since last polio case, A Jazeera 2012).

Indians are also particularly at high risk for atherosclerosis and coronary artery disease. This may bear tribute to a genetic predisposition to metabolic syndrome and changes in coronary artery vasodilatation. NGOs such as the Indian Heart Foundation and the Medwin Foundation have been created to raise awareness about this public health issue (Heart Disease is preventable, Indian Heart Foundation 2012; Preventindia.org 2012).

High Infant Mortality Rate

Infant mortality occurs when a child dies after birth. Childhood mortality is the death of a child before their fifth birthday. Approximately 1.72 million children die each year before turning one (Sharma). The under-five mortality and infant mortality rates have been declining, from 202 and 190 deaths per thousand live births respectively in 1970 to 64 and 50 deaths per thousand live births in 2009 (Maternal & Child Mortality and Tatal Fertility Rates 2012). However, this rate of decline is slowing. Reduced funding for immunization leaves only 43.5 per cent of the young fully immunized. A study conducted by the Future Health Systems Consortium in Murshidabad, West Bengal indicates that barriers to immunization coverage are adverse geographic location, absent or inadequately trained health workers and low perceived need for immunization Karjilid et al. 2009). Infrastructure like hospitals, roads, water and sanitation are lacking in rural areas (Medical and Healthcare

major cities that account for about nearly 90 per cent of this sectors exports are Bangalore, Chennai, Delhi, Mumbai, Hyderabad, Pune, Kolkata (The Indian IT Sector Analysis 2011)

This concept of using sophisticated Informational technology and penetration of IT usage made India a global business unit and made online business as the order of the day. IT became a backbone to all businesses and used as a cost-cutting strategy in order to withstand the competition. IT sector created employment opportunities and forced the Educational sector to meet the demand by adopting new curriculum. Sustaining global economic development will demand a substantial shift in the role of industry by bringing innovation to drive sustainability and profit.

India's rapid emergence as a global economic player is being propelled in large substance by its business and industry sector, which is increasingly contributing innovative solutions for integration of development and environmental sustainability. Because of innovativeness by the Indian Entrepreneurs, new products are coming into the market. Indian businessmen are competing with foreigners by entering into global bidding and acquiring foreign markets. Indian business companies are listed in foreign stock markets and doing a very good business. 'Made in India' became a serious business perspective.

THE ROLE OF URBANIZATION

Population residing in urban area, according to 1901 census, was 11.4 per cent (Singh 1978). This count increased to 28.53 per cent according to 2001 census, and crossing 30 per cent as per 2011 census, standing at 31.16 per cent (Business Standard 2012; Datta 2012). According to a survey by UN State of the World Population report in 2007, by 2030, 40.76 per cent of the country's population is expected to reside in urban areas (Urbanisation in India faster than rest of the world, Hindustan Times 2007). Urbanization made India to shift its focus from agricultural sector to manufacturing sector and now to

Service sector. When we opened our economy, we invited not only the international businesses but also the issues related to them. People enjoyed when the job market was open due to outsourcing business but people were realized later how it affected the lifestyles of them. Society has shifted from single-earning member to dual-earning members and this had a positive impact in changing their economic status from lower middle class to upper middle class but has a negative impact on personal front as they may be unable to adjust to work-life balance. As people are unable to find time for direct social interaction, online social networks became popular.

Health care became an emerging sector and is making a good business in the market. The awareness regarding health care among the people has increased. In fact, the health care businesses made it by creating awareness. To overcome from the problems related change in lifestyle, alternative medicines become more popular and this may be a kind of Lessing in disguise. Morning joggers, Gym visitors, Yoga followers, Ayush Care Centres, Body slimming centres became the order of the day. Indian markets by Foreign direct Investments (FDIs) and also grabbing the Indian businesses by Mergers & Acquisitions.

DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE

The development of science has a role even in health care sector from drug discovery to delivery. The R&D labs are in collaboration with foreign companies and introduced new technology, modern instruments and new drugs. Harifkine Institute (India's one of the oldest institute established in 1899) could produce some vaccines in 1947. Today India is engaged in developing recombinant and edible vaccines. Parma companies like Reddy's, Cipla and Rambaxy are giving the global pharma majors, a run for their money www.in.kpmg.com/pdf/Indian%20pharma%20outlook.pdf. A few small drug companies were producing a

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to medicine rural health or rural medicine is the interdisciplinary study of health and Health care delivery in the context of a rural environment or location. Some of the fields of study comprising rural health include health, geography, midwifery, nursing, sociology, economic and the health telemedicine. Rural India contains one-third per cent of India's total population with half of it living below poverty line, struggling for better and easy access to health care and services (Indiafact.net).

Health issues con-fronted by rural people are diverse and many—from severe malaria to uncontrolled diabetes, from a badly infected wound to cancer (Jeebhansur.org). Post-partum maternal morbidity is a serious problem in resource-poor settings and contributes to maternal mortality, particularly in rural India (Sutherland and Ezzati 2008). A study conducted in 2009, found that 43.9 per cent of mothers reported to have experienced post-partum morbidities six weeks after delivery (Taddebanam, Raimann, Singh, Barman and Kamjial 2010). Rural medical practitioners are highly sought after by people living in rural India as they more financially attractive and geographically accessible than practitioners working in the formal public health care sector (Kamjial 2007).

Sanitation is the hygienic means of promoting health through prevention of human contact with the faecal or other wastes. It can be physical, microbiological, biological or chemical agents of disease. The World Health Organization states that: 'Sanitation generally refers to the provision of facilities and services for the hygienic disposal of human excreta and faeces. Inadequate sanitation is a major cause of disease world-wide and one of the world's sanitation' also refers to the maintenance of hygienic conditions, through services such as sewerage, collection and wastewater (Kishore 2005). As more than 122 million households have no toilets, and 230 million lack access to latrines, over 50 per cent of the population (638 million) defecate in the open (Water, Environment and Sanitation, UNICEF India 2011). This is relatively higher than Bangladesh and Brazil (7 per cent and 9 per cent, respectively), although 200 million people gained access to improved sanitation from 1990 to 2008 with 3 per cent access them. Eleven per cent of the Indian rural families dispose of stools safely whereas 80 per cent of the population leave their stools in the open or throw them in the garbage (Water, Environment and Sanitation, UNICEF India 2011). Open air defecation leads to the spread of diseases and malnutrition through faecal and bacterial infections (Initiatives: Hygiene and Sanitation, Sangam (July to Action 2011).

Inadequate Safe Drinking Water

Drinking water or potable water is water safe enough to be consumed by humans or used with low risk of contamination or long term harm. Access to protected sources of drinking water has improved from 68 per cent of the population in 1990 to 88 per cent in 2008 (Water, Environment and Sanitation, UNICEF India 2011). However, only 26 per cent of the slum population has access to safe drinking water and 25 per cent of the population has drinking water on their premises. This problem is exacerbated by falling levels of groundwater caused mainly by increasing extraction for irrigation. Insufficient maintenance of the environment around water sources, groundwater pollution, excessive arsenic and fluoride in drinking water pose a major threat to India's health.

Rural Health

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WOMAN'S HEALTH ISSUES

According to tradition in India, women requires to eat hot even during pregnancy and lactating period, which is the main cause of female infirmity or health hazard and the status of women in India

- 1. Women's health
- 2. One of the most growing problems among women causing an increased number of mortality rates in India
- 3. Anemia
- 4. Pregnancy related deaths (PRD)

PRD is another form causing increase in mortality rate in females. It is a condition in which there are many malarias in the uterus, which can affect a woman's ability to conceive.

Women's Awareness

India's national mortality rates in total area are highest amongst the world.

GLOBALIZATION IN INDIA

Globalization, Privatization and Liberalization (G.P.L) has its impact on people in India and has resulted in new ways of India to foreign markets. The term globalization means international integration. It includes an array of social, political and economic changes. Unimaginable progress in modes of communications, transportation and computer technology, and have given the process a new lease of life.

The image of India among the foreign nations has changed from a 'poor country' to an advanced knowledge hub.

THE MAIN FACTORS FOR SUCH A DRAMATIC CHANGE ARE

- 1. Rise in Information Technology (IT), changing the face of India,
- 2. Innovation in business,
- 3. Innovativeness in controlling the economy, irrespective of political changes in the government,
- 4. Innovativeness among people due to the free environment created by implementing the freedom by all means approved as per Indian Constitution.
- 5. Inherent intelligence among the people because of the traditional culture and heritage of the country (www.imsi.org) (12)

RISE IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (IT), CHANGING FACE OF INDIA

Today Indians are changing terms to global IT industry. NRI venture capitalists are well established in the Silicon Valley. IT firms like TCS, INFOSYS and WIPRO are global brands. There is a huge demand for skilled Indian IT professionals. This is normal for our country because we gifted the game of Chess and the concept of zero to the world (Narant 2006). The information technology industry in India has gained brand identity as knowledge economy due to its IT and IITES sector.

THE IT-ITES INDUSTRY HAS TWO MAJOR COMPONENTS

IT services and business process outsourcing (BPO). The growth in the service sector in India has been led by the IT-ITES sectors, contributing substantially to increase in GDP, employment and exports. The sector has increased its contribution to India's GDP from 1.2 per cent in FY 1998 to 7.5 per cent in FY 2012 (Indian IT-ITES Industry). According to NASSCOM, the IT-ITES sector in India aggregated revenues of US\$ 100 billion in Y 2012, where export and domestic revenue stood at US\$ 60.1 billion and US\$ 31.7 billion respectively, growing by over 9 per cent. The

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